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School of Mathematics, Statistics
and Actuarial Science

CAPSTONE PROJECT DISSERTATION

EVALUATING TIME SERIES AND
NEURAL NETWORK TECHNIQUES
FOR PREDICTIVE MODELLING USING
COVID-19 DATA: INSIGHTS FROM
ARIMA, PROPHET, RNN AND LSTM
APPROACHES

OLUTOMIWA ADEBAMINLE ADELIYI

REG. No: 2213139

Supervisor: **DR. JOSEPH BAILEY**

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Colchester

Abstract

This dissertation investigates the temporal dynamics of COVID-19 using time series techniques, focusing on confirmed cases, deaths, and recoveries. It also analyses seasonality and cyclic patterns, evaluates the impact of data granularity, and compares traditional time series models with deep learning methods. Key findings indicate notable variations in COVID-19 trends among the countries studied and demonstrates greater precision of deep learning models over traditional methods.

Contents

1	INTRODUCTION	6
2	LITERATURE REVIEW	10
2.1	Time Series Forecasting and Deep Learning	10
2.2	COVID-19 Data and Predictive Modelling	11
2.2.1	ARIMA For COVID-19 Predictive Modelling	12
2.2.2	Facebook Prophet For COVID-19 Predictive Modelling	13
2.2.3	RNN and LSTM For COVID-19 Predictive Modelling	14
3	DATASET AND METHODOLOGY	16
3.1	Dataset Description and Preprocessing Techniques	16
3.2	Exploratory Data Analysis	17
3.3	Methodology	19
3.4	Mathematical Overview of Models	20
3.4.1	ARIMA:Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average	20
3.4.2	Prophet: Forecasting With Seasonal Decomposition	22
3.4.3	RNN: Recurrent Neural Networks	23
3.4.4	LSTM: Long Short-Term Memory Networks	25
3.4.5	Evaluation Metrics	26
4	RESULTS	28
5	DISCUSSION	37
A	APPENDICES	53

List of Abbreviations

3D Three-Dimensional

ACF Auto Correlation Function

ARIMA AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average

CNN Convolutional Neural Network

COVID-19 Coronavirus Disease 2019

ECDC European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control

ICU Intensive Care Unit

LSTM Long Short-Term Memory

MERS Middle East Respiratory Syndrome

PACF Partial Auto Correlation Function

RNN Recurrent Neural Network

SARS Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome

SARS-CoV-2 Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2

STL Seasonal-Trend decomposition using LOESS

UK United Kingdom

US United States

List of Figures

3.1	Growth Rate of Confirmed COVID-19 Cases	18
3.2	Recovery Growth Rate Over Time	18
3.3	Death Growth Rate Over Time	19
4.1	Comparison of MAE Distribution: Daily Vs Weekly	35
4.2	Comparison of MAE Distribution: Traditional Vs Deep Learning Models	36
A.1	ACF and PACF for United States Confirmed Cases	53
A.2	ACF and PACF for France Confirmed Cases	53
A.3	ACF and PACF for US Death Cases	54
A.4	ACF and PACF for India Death Cases	54
A.5	ACF and PACF for France Death Cases	54
A.6	ACF and PACF for US Recovered Cases	55
A.7	ACF and PACF for India Recovered Cases	55
A.8	ACF and PACF For France Recovered Cases	55

List of Tables

4.1	A. Stationarity Test Results for Confirmed Cases, Deaths, and Recovered Cases	29
4.2	Mean Absolute Error (MAE) for Daily and Weekly Confirmed Cases	32
4.3	MAE for Daily and Weekly Death Cases	33
4.4	MAE for Daily and Weekly Recovered Cases	34
4.5	Overview of Model with Lowest MAE per Country and Category	34
A.1	Optimal ARIMA Orders for Daily and Weekly COVID-19 Data	56
A.2	Optimal ARIMA Orders for Daily and Weekly COVID-19 Data	56
A.3	Best Parameters for Prophet Model	57
A.4	Best Parameters for RNN Models	58
A.5	Best Parameters for LSTM Models	59

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic started in Wuhan, China, back in December 2019 and quickly spread all over the world [1,2]. It was a type of pandemic that the entire world had never seen nor dealt with before and it affected the health services, economies, and societies everywhere. A number of researchers have pointed out how this pandemic impacted the world's economy and affected people's lives. For instance, Rahman et al [3] took a close look at how travel and tourism around the world was negatively affected by the pandemic and all the resulting lock downs. Wang et al [4] studied how staying at home during the pandemic affected the kids in China, and they even suggested some ways to ease the impact on these kids [4]. Jribi and et al [5] wrote about how the pandemic changed the way households handle food items and how much of the food were wasted during the pandemic.

COVID-19 is the third virus of its kind to come from animals, after SARS and MERS and it is caused by a new virus called SARS-CoV-2 [6]. But this particular variant is different because it has the ability to cause a global pandemic [6]. The World Health Organisation states that, as of October 15, 2023, the COVID-19 virus has killed nearly seven million people and infected over 771 million [7]. As countries try to navigate the difficult aftermath of this pandemic, using predictive modelling to anticipate what will happen next regarding the pandemic has become important. Predictive modelling can be used to depict or show the future patterns of the COVID-19 virus, such as when infectious cases and deaths may rise or fall [8,9]. With this information, governments and healthcare organisations can know when to act fast with medical help, when to

tighten or relax rules like lock downs, and can even predict or forecast when the next wave of the virus might hit the world again [8].

Being able to anticipate major or disruptive events in healthcare is important. It helps healthcare professionals and governments plan for the equipment they may need, like masks and ventilators, where to send medical staff, and how to respond quickly to new challenges that may arise during a crisis similar to the COVID-19 [10].

Even though the world has come a long way in dealing with COVID-19, the omicron variant, which is a changed version of the original virus, has got everyone worried because it seems to spread faster and might not be stopped by the vaccines that are currently available. The World Health Organization has even called it a "variant of concern" [11, 12]. In 2023, the United Kingdom saw the virus making a comeback. By June 2023, more people were getting infected every day and the number of positive tests went up [13]. This emphasises the need for ongoing research to study and understand the virus. Predictive modelling is essential, as it could help anticipate the pandemic's future course accurately. With good predictions, healthcare leaders and governments can make smarter and more informed choices like planning medical responses, deciding when to implement measures like lock downs, and preparing for possible future outbreaks [8, 10].

Predictive modelling is very useful in the health care sector due to its multifaceted applications [14]. It can be used in early disease detection as it can take old patient records and use them to identify potential or new diseases, which means doctors can treat people sooner before the disease becomes worse or degenerates [15]. Also, predictive modelling helps governments, hospitals, clinics and medical stakeholders figure out how to effectively manage their resources, like beds and staff based on how many patients they expect and the type of sicknesses [10, 14, 15]. By looking at a person's medical history and genes, predictive models assist in creating treatments regimen that work well without too many side effects [16].

These models are very useful for predicting epidemic outbreaks, forecasting health crises and for providing insight for formulating preventive measures [17]. Also, when it comes to health administration, knowing what to expect with diseases and patient care helps governments and hospitals make informed financial decisions, optimise their budgets and curtail or expunge unwarranted and unnecessary expenses [18]. As

implied earlier, previous research efforts have been directed towards the COVID-19 pandemic, ranging from the search for optimal treatments, the development of effective vaccines [19, 20] to using mathematical models to figure out how the virus might spread [21].

Researchers have been using a range of statistical, machine learning, deep learning, and mathematical modeling techniques to predict the spread patterns and transmission dynamics of COVID-19 [8]. Early in 2020, Yonar et al used the ARIMA and Brown/Holt linear exponential smoothing models to estimate the number of COVID-19 cases in the major G8 countries and found them useful, especially for understanding the trajectory in Turkey [22]. There is also the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks a subset of deep learning models that is being used due to its predictive ability [23]. Sardar et al [24] published a research on the potential of machine learning in forecasting COVID-19's impact by using different machine learning models like ARIMA, GLMNet, random forest and XGBoost to see how good they were at predicting the pandemic's effects around the world and in specific regions. They found out that ARIMA was one of the best for looking at trends in several SAARC countries [24]. ARIMA is not perfect as some researchers have pointed out that it might not work well with non-linear data especially in complicated situations [25]. Specifically, a major issue with ARIMA is that it cannot handle nonlinear patterns which can be found in real world data [26].

In this study, I am going to investigate the trends of COVID-19 cases, including the rates of confirmed cases, deaths and recoveries over time. I will be using traditional time series methods and deep learning approaches to understand these trends better .

My goal is to test these approaches and see how factors such as seasonal changes, repeating patterns and whether we look at the COVID-19 numbers on a daily or weekly basis impact the accuracy of our predictions.

The objectives of this research include:

1. Analysing the temporal dynamics of COVID-19 confirmed, death and recovery rates using time series techniques.
2. Investigating the presence of seasonality or cyclic patterns in COVID-19 confirmed, death and recovery rates to provide more context to its evolution over time.
3. Determining the influence of data granularity, particularly the contrast between

daily and weekly data, on the prediction accuracy of the models.

4. Evaluating the effectiveness of traditional time series models versus deep learning models in forecasting COVID-19 outcomes.

To the best of my knowledge, few studies have holistically approached using both time series methods and deep learning models to predict the dynamics of the COVID-19 cases, death and recoveries [8,24,25,27]. I believe that this research will stimulate further studies, encouraging the validation or refinement of this study.

The structure of this study is as follows. Section 2 provides the literature review that discusses the significance of time series forecasting and deep learning in the context of COVID-19. Section 3 offers a detailed exploration of the data used in this research: its origins, the preprocessing steps undertaken and the insights from the exploratory data analysis and also lays out the research methodology and contains detailed mathematical overview of the models that are relevant to this study (ARIMA, Prophet, RNN, and LSTM) and the evaluation metrics used. Section 4 presents the findings post model implementation. It show the results, compares the performances of the models and also provides insights into the trajectory of COVID-19 based on the analysis. Section 5 rounds off the study with conclusions, highlighting key takeaways and avenues worth exploring in future research.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Time Series Forecasting and Deep Learning

Time series forecasting is an ideal approach in statistical and machine learning methodologies to predict future values based on historically observed data points in time [28]. It is useful across many research fields such as meteorology, demography, public health, computing and finance. The fact that it is applicable to a several of real world challenges has made it a favourite of several researchers, particularly within the financial sector where accurate predictions of stock market trends is important [29]. Furthermore Das [30] opined that current and historical data have become a foundational pillar of time series forecasting [30]. Time series analysis has a rich history that dates back to the late 19th and early 20th centuries, where pioneering economists established the foundational principles by decomposing time series into essential components (trends, seasonal variations, and cyclical fluctuations), they provided a framework for interpreting complex data through time [31]. Around the 20th century statisticians like Karl Pearson started to dive into autocorrelation. Pearson helped explain how a set of data points can be related to its past values [32]. The 1920s marked a big change when people like G. Udny Yule [33] moved away from just breaking down data. Instead, they began to build models that could predict future trends and that really shaped the way we forecast today [33]. George E. P. Box and Gwilym M. Jenkins co developed the Box-Jenkins methodology, an iterative approach designed for identifying, estimating

and checking models for time series forecasting in 1970 with the seminal work "Time Series Analysis: Forecasting and Control" [34].

Even though the way we forecast using time series data has come a long way, there are still some challenges that are faced. For instance, seasonality which happens when the data shows predictable changes at certain times of the year [35]. Models have to be able to handle these regular ups and downs [36]. Another challenge is when data does not stay the same over time, which is called non-stationarity. A lot of the statistical models need data to be consistent but in the real world it is never static [37].

Then there is the issue of noise and unusual values in the data that can disrupt the forecasts. That is why cleaning up the data carefully is a fundamental task [38]. Using different methods to smooth out and filter the data helps make the models efficient and more accurate [39].

2.2 COVID-19 Data and Predictive Modelling

The COVID-19 outbreak has pushed the need for data modelling to help public health officials make important decisions [8]. This subsection provides a review of existing research related to COVID-19 data sources, preprocessing techniques, predictive modelling methodologies, performance evaluation and emerging research directions. A detailed review of what is already known is key to understanding why this study is being done, what it aims to find out and how it plans to go about it. Being able to predict the spread of infectious diseases accurately and on time helps leaders make strategic decisions about how to control disease, manage resources efficiently and ultimately help save lives [8].

Lots of organisations like the Health Data Research UK [40] have put together COVID-19 databases that researchers can use. These databases get their information from places like government departments, groups working together and healthcare networks. For instance, the CDC in the US shares detailed data that is updated regularly. This includes information on cases, deaths, testing, hospital stays, vaccinations, and demographic details [41]. The ECDC does the same thing for countries in the European Union by offering regional data sets that have similar variables for European Union member states [42]. The Johns Hopkins University Coronavirus Resource Center also

collects and aggregates data from different sources and shares it in an easy to use format on GitHub. The data is updated every day and is useful for conducting global analysis [43]. Then there are healthcare networks like the Mayo Clinic which have their own COVID-19 resource centers. These provide databases and reports filled with clinical information that can help in understanding how the virus spreads [44].

Before analysis, data typically undergoes preprocessing steps to standardise formats, handle missing data, imbalance, duplicates and anomalies [45]. Researchers often use several methods to fill in missing healthcare data. Some popular ones are Expectation Maximization (EM), which estimates the missing values using a statistical model, Multivariate Imputation by Chained Equations (MICEs), which fills in missing values by creating multiple possible complete data sets, K-Nearest Neighbors Imputation, which finds the closest matches to a missing value from the other available data, and mean imputation, which simply replaces missing values with the average of the available ones [46]. To deal or handle with unpredictable daily changes and to see the broader trends, smoothing methods like calculating moving averages are used on the number of cases [47].

2.2.1 ARIMA For COVID-19 Predictive Modelling

With so much data available on COVID-19, researchers have used different methods to try and predict various outcomes of the COVID-19 virus. One technique that has been really helpful is the The auto regressive integrated moving averag (ARIMA) model. By modelling auto correlations, ARIMA can uncover patterns in lagged observations to forecast future pandemic trends [48,49]. Early on, researchers saw that ARIMA models could be useful at making projection tasks. For instance, Ceylan used the ARIMA to model the confirmed cases of the outbreak in European hot spots like Italy, Spain, and France. He formulated several ARIMA models with different ARIMA parameters and wrote that ARIMA (0,2,1), ARIMA (1,2,0), and ARIMA (0,2,1) models with the lowest MAPE values of 4.7520, 5.8486, and 5.6335 were the best for predicting confirmed cases in Italy, Spain, and France, respectively [50]. Gupta et al also applied an ARIMA (1,1,2) to data from India and were able to predict the virus's path for April 2020 by using information from earlier months [51]. As more data became available, researchers started to try out different kinds of ARIMA models like the seasonal ARIMA (SARIMA)

which is designed to consider regular patterns that happen over time like those that can be seen with COVID-19 cases. ArunKumar et al found that SARIMA was good at capturing seasonal variations/patterns in many of the major epicenters of the virus [52]. However, in contrast, Konarasinghe pointed out that SARIMA underperformed the Sama Circular Model (SCM) in identifying seasonal trends in the Italian outbreak [53].

Beyond forecasting, ARIMA models have also been really useful for helping to shape health policies. For instance, Alzahrani et al identified ARIMA(2,1,1) as optimal for predicting how COVID-19 would spread in Saudi Arabia before the Hajj in 2020 which was very valuable for the authorities to plan and prepare for the event planning [54].

To enhance predictive ability, researchers have augmented ARIMA with machine learning, leveraging complementary strengths. Barman [55] combined LSTM neural networks with ARIMA, attaining comparable results to stand alone ARIMA. However, the integration improved responsiveness to pandemic non-linearities [55]. Istaiteh et al similarly coupled ARIMA with LSTM and CNN models for global forecasting, the results showed the benefits of integrating statistical and deep learning techniques [56].

2.2.2 Facebook Prophet For COVID-19 Predictive Modelling

Prophet, an open source forecasting tool which was developed internally by Facebook's Sean J. Taylor and Ben Letham in 2017 has emerged as a popular forecasting tool tailored for data sets that exhibit strong seasonal patterns, holidays effects, or other recurring events [57,58]. Its ability to handle missing data and outliers positions it as a robust tool, especially in the unpredictable nature of the COVID-19 pandemic [59].

Mahmud et al used the prophet model to examine COVID-19 trends. Remarkably, the model was able to make accurate predictions about how the virus was spreading, the number of deaths, and patients recoveries. It could even predict the impact of the virus after specific periods like 15 and 45 days with about 92 percent accuracy [60].

A significant feature of prophet is its flexibilities. As described by Rafferty, prophet allows users to add custom seasonalities and holiday effects [58]. Researchers have taken advantage of this aspect of the prophet model to factor in special events like public gatherings and/or travel restrictions. By doing so they have been able to tweak their predictions to be more specific and accurate for how COVID-19 spreads. [24].

Although the Facebook prophet model is good at forecasting trends, it is not without

its challenges. Specifically, when confronted with a lack of distinct daily and yearly seasonality data the model might struggle to give detailed predictions [15]. Despite these challenges the Facebook Prophet model continues to be useful in forecasting future cumulative COVID-19 infections.

There is a way to make the Prophet model even better by combining it with other models. For example, Wang et al demonstrated that one can take a number called the 'cap value' from a Logistic model and use it to improve the prophet models' predictions [61]. Borges et al went into more detail, specifically looking at predicting the need for ICU beds during the pandemic. They introduced an Integrated Multivariate Prophet-LSTM approach that considers both traditional time series patterns and an array of explanatory and correlated variables across optimal time lags. Their findings shows that the two stage integration of Prophet and LSTM significantly improved the forecasting of ICU demands, out performing using the Prophet or LSTM alone. [62].

2.2.3 RNN and LSTM For COVID-19 Predictive Modelling

Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) have become really useful for time series forecasting due to their ability to process sequences of data and retain memory from previous inputs [63,64]. More specifically, during the COVID-19 outbreak, RNNs have been key to figuring out how the virus spreads over time [63,64].

Even though RNNs are great at dealing with sequences of data, it can be tough to train them on longer sequences. This is because they start to forget the errors they need to learn from. A problem known as vanishing gradients [52]. They are particularly praised for finding patterns over time which is important for understanding infectious disease modelling [65]. Lee et al for example used an RNN to predict severe outcomes in COVID-19 patients by looking at their historical Electronic Health Record data. Their RNN attained the top average AUC although its performance margin over other baselines was not significantly pronounced. This might be because they did not have a lot of data to work with [66]. One pressing concern with their RNN model was that it compromised interpretability, which is important when handling medical data [66].

LSTMs which are a form of specialized RNNs possess an ability to correct the limitations that are inherent in traditional time series forecasting methodologies. Their structure is appropriate for managing the complex and non linear patterns observable

within the COVID-19 data sets leading to innovative achievements in processing time related data. These units sequentially pass information, culminating in an aggregate result [67]. At the heart of the LSTM's architecture are the memory blocks designed to bypass the issue of diminishing gradients thus preserving the integrity of the network parameters across longer durations. In their study, Chimmula et al. [67] leveraged an LSTM-based deep learning framework to predict the trajectory of the pandemic in Canada with their projections showing a remarkable shortterm precision of 93.4percent and a long term precision of 92.67 percent.

Additionally, the evolution of hybrid models that merge LSTMs with other algorithms has been noted. Barman, for instance combined LSTM with ARIMA to better interpret the non-linear progression characteristic of the pandemic's spread [55]. Nonetheless, the application of LSTMs is not without its challenges. As Xie et al. have pointed out, these deep learning models demand substantial computational resources and time for training which is a significant consideration [68].

DATASET AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Dataset Description and Preprocessing Techniques

For this research, data from the GitHub repository of the Center for Systems Science and Engineering (CSSE) at Johns Hopkins University [69] that was earlier mentioned above was obtained. This data was retrieved on October 15, 2023 at 10:13 AM.

The dataset consists of daily updated figures for confirmed cases, deaths and recoveries from all countries around the world. For clarity, the data was grouped by country. The geographical location details, longitude and latitude were dropped because they were not important for this study. The totals for each country were easy to compile since the data was presented in a cumulative form by including previous counts in the total.

The data was narrowed down to three countries with the highest reported numbers of confirmed COVID-19 cases: the United States, India, and France. The data source is believed to be accurate considering the global reputation of the data source. The top 3 countries by confirmed cases provides a representative sample for this study. The initial data set from this analysis contained 1143 rows and 10 columns of data. The data had no missing data points and no duplicates were found. The data was re-arranged so that dates were listed in rows and the column headers were also changed to make them clearer as the initial data had a multi-index header.

3.2 Exploratory Data Analysis

As part of the exploratory data analysis phase, cumulative plots were generated for confirmed cases, recoveries and deaths to examine their progression over time. The visual representation showed that there was a very sharp drop in recoveries for the United States shortly before January 2021 and for India in August 2022, using data for recoveries beyond this point could distort the prediction results. This and data sufficiency therefore, influenced the decision on the choice of the dataset's timeframe for further analysis to the data from May 1, 2020, to December 31, 2020. This period is made up of 245 days of daily records and comprises 10 rows for date, confirmed cases, recoveries and death. The Inter Quartile Range (IQR) method and box plots were used to identify outliers within the data across the three countries. We decided not to drop the outliers as they represent less than one percent of the data set. The heatmap gave a graphical overview of the variation between and within the data set. The daily growth rate for each of the three countries was calculated and visualised to assess the pandemic's trajectory. Cumulative case counts were again plotted for each country to compare the pandemics progression for the period chosen for further analysis. The recovery growth rate, again showed a sharp drop for the US in December.

During the exploratory data analysis, we investigated the temporal dynamics of the COVID-19 confirmed, death and recovery rates using time series graphs and growth rate graphs.

CONFIRMED CASES

Fig 3.1, below shows growth rate for the confirmed cases in the countries of focus. For the US, it is clear from the graph that the growth rate of confirmed cases declines a little initially but then stabilises with some fluctuation.

India's confirmed case growth rate starts higher than the other two countries, decreases but then shows some form of stability in declining. The highest growth rate for India in the period under review is May 2020. France exhibits a pattern with several peaks and dips, showing waves in confirmed cases. Coincidentally, the highest and lowest growth of confirmed cases in France were both in November 2020.

Of the three countries, France has the lowest initial growth rate while India has

Figure 3.1: Growth Rate of Confirmed COVID-19 Cases

the highest initial growth rate. Between August and September 2020 the growth rate of confirmed cases in the US and France exhibited similar trends. Overall, while the growth rate in the US was generally stable for the period under review, the growth rate in India though fluctuating was declining.

RECOVERED CASES

Fig 3.2 below shows the recovery growth rate. The recovery rate for the US starts at a lower level in May, gradually increasing very slowly to reach almost a plateau by December. It then declines in December before plateauing again in the same month. This may affect the predictive accuracy of the models for the US recovery cases.

Figure 3.2: Recovery Growth Rate Over Time

In India, the recovery rate increases at a steady pace for our review period, indicating a very high recovery rate and almost reaching a growth rate of 1 at the end of the year. France’s recovery rate starts similarly to the US but then exhibits a downward trend from August. Overall India had a consistently high recovery rate compared to the other two countries. While the recovery rates declined in France in August, that of the US only sharply declined in December 2020.

DEATH CASES

The death rate was highest in France and the death rate in France was more than twice the death rate in the US and India. The death rate for the three countries plateaued in November 2023. France also shows the highest initial death rate which begins to decrease in August 2020 and sharply declines between September and November 2020 and then remains relatively flat from November to December.

Figure 3.3: Death Growth Rate Over Time

The US shows a declining trend from May to December with a consistent reduction. India’s death rate was the lowest and generally flattens out at a lower rate .

3.3 Methodology

To ensure the suitability of the time series data for ARIMA modelling, the cumulative data was tested for stationarity and then differenced. The first differencing achieved stationarity for most of the columns, however, there was a need to difference the

columns that did not achieve initial stationarity again. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller test was used to confirm the stationarity of the series through the Auto Correlation Function (ACF) and the Partial Auto Correlation Function (PACF) plots.

To address the research question on granularity, the weekly data set was created from the existing data set. For predictive modelling, the dataset was divided into training and testing sets. The forecast horizon for the daily data was set to 7 days and for the weekly data to 2 weeks. The `auto_arima` function was used to find the optimal parameters for the ARIMA model, based on the training data. This process ignores seasonality. The ARIMA model is then fitted with the optimal parameters. The model makes forecasts for the specified forecast horizon. The model's forecasts are compared against the actual values in the testing set.

In a similar approach, the Facebook's Prophet model was applied for forecasting our data using the same forecast horizon, while focusing on optimising its parameters to improve the accuracy through a gridsearch that identifies the best combination of change point and seasonality scales.

For the neural network based time series analysis, a single function was used to preprocess the data, creating sequences of a specified length and structuring them into 3D arrays suitable for both Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models. The RNN model defined with two layers of 50 units each was subjected to a manual grid search for optimal hyperparameters and then trained over 100 epochs. Similarly, the LSTM model also with two layers of 50 units was trained for the same duration.

3.4 Mathematical Overview of Models

3.4.1 ARIMA: Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average

The ARIMA model which stands for Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average was formally introduced in a seminal 1970 paper by statisticians George Box and Gwilym Jenkins [70]. Building on the foundational work by Yule [33] and Wold [71], Box and Jenkins [70] pioneered a methodology for constructing ARIMA models. This approach marked an unforgettable shift in the field of time series analysis and forecasting techniques. The Box-Jenkins method revolves around three intertwined stages: model identi-

fication, parameter estimation and diagnostic validation [36].

At its core, model identification is anchored on the premise that a time series if derived from an ARIMA process should inherently exhibit certain theoretical auto correlation traits [36]. By comparing empirical auto correlation patterns with these theoretical expectations, analysts can often pinpoint one or multiple viable models tailored to a particular time series [36]. To aid in this model order determination, Box and Jenkins [70] championed the use of the auto correlation function in combination with the partial auto correlation function derived from sample data. In the auto regressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) model, the future value of a variable is represented as a linear combination of its historical values and stochastic errors, expressed in the following manner [36]:

Mathematical Framework of ARIMA

$$y_t = \phi y_{t-1} + \dots + \phi_p y_{t-p} + \epsilon_t - \theta \epsilon_{t-1} - \dots - \theta_q \epsilon_{t-q} \quad (3.1)$$

[36,72]

where:

- y_t and ϵ_t are the actual value and random error at time period t , respectively;
- ϕ and θ are model parameters [36,72].
- p and q are integers and often referred to as the orders of the model [36,72].
- ϵ_t are Random Errors and represent the holiday effect, modeling predictable irregular occurrences [36,72].
- ϵ_t assumed to be independently and identically distributed with a mean of zero and a constant variance of σ^2 [36,72]

The ARIMA model is very popular for making time series forecasting in many areas. In Economics for instance, ARIMA is useful because of its flexibility in modeling trends and seasonality, making it great for forecasting or predicting macroeconomic indicators like GDP, inflation, and unemployment rates [73]. In Finance, ARIMA models are usually used to forecast stochastic market variables including asset prices, returns, and volatility [74]. Businesses use ARIMA to plan for sales, demand and inventory

forecasting where series display predictable cyclical patterns [75]. Meteorologists and climatologists apply ARIMA techniques to weather forecasting for temperature, rainfall, and other data [76]. Electricity companies use ARIMA models for short term load forecasting and for also predicting electricity demand [77]. Healthcare researchers use ARIMA to forecast medical time series like disease rates for public health planning [78]. It may be inferred from the above that the continued use of ARIMA in various fields may be due to its predictive accuracy.

3.4.2 Prophet: Forecasting With Seasonal Decomposition

Facebook Prophet is an off-the-shelf tool for time series forecasting that is useful when dealing with seasonal data. It is an open-source library developed by Facebook's Sean J. Taylor and Ben Letham [57–59]. It is designed to be easy to use, so that non experts can also use it in predicting trends. Facebook Prophet is useful for data that follow regular patterns throughout the year. It is also good at handling unexpected changes or one off events that might throw off the forecasting accuracy of other forecasting tools [79, 80]. To use Facebook prophet, data needs to be arranged into a table with just two columns, 'ds', which stands for the date stamp and should be in datetime format, and 'y' which represents the value to be forecast. specific instructions are provided to prophet regarding the extent of the future prediction required. Once done, prophet displays its prediction [79, 80].

Mathematical Framework of Prophet

The Prophet model is defined by the equation:

$$y(t) = g(t) + s(t) + h(t) + \epsilon_t$$

[57–59] where:

- $y(t)$ is the additive regressive model.
- $g(t)$ represents the trend component, capturing whether the series is increasing or decreasing over time.
- $s(t)$ accounts for seasonality, modeling periodic changes such as weekly, monthly, or yearly fluctuations.

- $h(t)$ represents the holiday effect, modeling predictable irregular occurrences.
- ϵ_t is the error term, representing unpredictable changes.

[57–59]

The Facebook prophet has also become quite popular for making time series forecasting in many areas. Khayyat et al [81] used it for stock prediction even though their result showed preference for the ARIMA model. That is in contrast to Jha et al who concluded that the Prophet was more effective for forecasting supermarket sales [82]. In the oil and gas sector, Guleryuz et al [83] deployed Prophet to predict the prices of the Brent crude oil. Despite being a new tool, Prophet appears to be gaining popularity for analysing time series data.

3.4.3 RNN: Recurrent Neural Networks

Deep learning models have shown superiority over statistical machine learning models for forecasting in nonlinear applications such as prediction of stock prices [84], electrocardiogram (ECG) recordings [85] and crude oil prices [86] among others. Feed Forward Neural Networks (FFNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) are two types of widely used deep learning techniques [87].

RNNs are particularly promising due to their internal memory which retains important features of input data thereby enabling accurate predictions [88, 89]. RNNs have connections that feed the output from the previous time step back into the network alongside the input from the current time step allowing the current state of the model to be influenced by its previous states [88, 89]. The following equation explains the function of a single RNN cell:

Mathematical Frameworks of RNN

In a typical feed forward multilayer neural network, an input vector is fed to neurons at the input layer which is then multiplied by an activation function to produce an intermediate neuron output [84, 86, 88, 89]. This output then becomes the input for the neuron in the next layer. The net input (denoted $input_sum_i$) for this neuron belonging to the next layer is the connection weight (W) times the output of the previous neuron plus a bias term [84, 86, 88, 89]. Then the activation function (denoted by g) is applied to

$input_sum_i$ to get the neuron output [84, 86, 88, 89].

$$input_sum_i = w_i x_i + b \quad (3.2)$$

[84, 86, 88, 89]

$$a_i = g(input_sum_i) \quad (3.3)$$

[84, 86, 88, 89]

$$a_i = g(w_i x_i + b) \quad (3.4)$$

[84, 86, 88, 89]

For each time step t , the activation $h_{(t)}$ and the output y_t are expressed as follows:

$$h_t = g_1(w_{hh}a_{t-1} + w_{hx}x_t + b_h) \quad (3.5)$$

[84, 86, 88, 89] and

$$y_t = g_2(w_{yh}h_t + b_y) \quad (3.6)$$

[84, 86, 88, 89] where w_{hx} , w_{hh} , w_{yh} , b_h and b_y are coefficients that are shared temporally and g_1 , g_2 are the activation functions.

$$w = w + \Delta w \quad (3.7)$$

$$\Delta w = n \frac{de}{dw} \quad (3.8)$$

[84, 86–89] where $e = (\text{Actual Output} - \text{Model Output})^2$

If $\frac{de}{dw} \ll 1 \Rightarrow \Delta w \ll 1$ and $w \ll 1$ (Vanishing)

But if $\frac{de}{dw} \gg 1 \Rightarrow \Delta w \gg 1$ and $w \gg 1$ (Exploding)

[84, 86–89]

Recurrent neural networks suffer from shortterm memory as vanishing gradients appear in RNNs due to their nature of being recursive and having deep layers. Since the weights are updated in proportion to the gradient, the vanishing gradient or small value will cause a slight change in the weight value. No change in value in the network means that it does not contribute much to learning. In short, training is useless. [84, 86–89]. To address these shortcomings, modifications such as Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) cells have been introduced. These architectures

incorporate mechanisms to allow for the capture and retention of information over longer periods and to effectively manage the flow of information through the network [84, 87–90].

3.4.4 LSTM: Long Short-Term Memory Networks

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks are a type of recurrent neural network, introduced in 1997 by Hochreiter and Schmidhuber to specifically address the issue of vanishing gradients in traditional RNN architectures [91]. LSTMs have since become one of the most popular and effective models for sequential data modeling tasks such as speech recognition, handwriting recognition, machine translation and time series forecasting [92].

The key advancement provided by LSTMs is the cell state, which acts as a memory cell that can maintain information over long periods of time [92, 93]. LSTMs also contain input, output and forget gates that allow the model to selectively store, utilize or discard information from the cell state. This gating mechanism gives LSTMs more control over the cell state compared to vanilla RNNs, where information tends to quickly vanish or explode over many time steps [92, 93].

The equations that govern the computations of the LSTM at each time step are as follows:

- Forget Gate: $f(t) = \sigma(W_f \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_f)$
- Input Gate: $i(t) = \sigma(W_i \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_i)$
- Cell State: $C_t = f(t) \cdot C_{t-1} + i(t) \cdot \tanh(W_C \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_C)$
- Output Gate: $o(t) = \sigma(W_o \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_o)$
- Hidden State: $h_t = o(t) \cdot \tanh(C_t)$

[92–95]

Where σ is the sigmoid activation function, \cdot represents element-wise multiplication, and W and b terms denote learned weight matrices and bias vectors.

The forget gate controls what information from the previous cell state C_{t-1} should be discarded. The input gate determines what new information from the current input

x_t should be stored in the cell state. The output gate filters the cell state to generate the hidden state output h_t . These mechanisms allow LSTMs to selectively preserve important long-term dependencies and discard irrelevant information [94, 95].

3.4.5 Evaluation Metrics

There are various methods that can be used for evaluating the results of predictive models. Evaluation metrics tell us how correctly our statistical model is performing [24] and they include the MAE, the MAPE, the MASE, the SMAPE, the RMSE and the Rsquare values as used by Sadar et al [24] and Kiganda et al [8]. I have opted for the Mean Absolute Error(MAE) as the evaluation metric of choice because the relative performance of the models remains consistent across the various metrics mentioned. In essence, since our objective is to rank the models based on their data fitting capabilities, the choice of metric does not affect their ranking order. For example, a method that results in a higher MAE will also tend to show higher values for other metrics such as MAPE, MASE, SMAPE, RMSE, and R-square thereby maintaining its rank positions relative to other methods.

The Mean Absolute Error (MAE)

Mean Absolute Error (MAE) is a fundamental metric for evaluating the performance of predictive models and it is particularly widely used for its clarity and interpretability. Unlike the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) which gives a relatively high weight to large errors, MAE treats all errors in a linear fashion providing a simple direct average of error magnitudes [8, 24, 96–98].

MAE is calculated by taking the average of the absolute differences between the predicted values and the actual observed values. By using the absolute value of these differences, MAE avoids issues related to error sign (positive or negative) ensuring that all errors are treated equally, whether they are under or over estimates. This characteristic of MAE makes it robust to outliers as it does not square the error values and therefore does not disproportionately penalize larger errors as RMSE does.

Mathematically, for a series of predictions \hat{y}_i and actual observations y_i , with n being

the total number of observations, MAE is calculated using the following formula:

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |\hat{y}_i - y_i| \quad (3.9)$$

[8,24,96–98]. In this formula, $|\hat{y}_i - y_i|$ represents the absolute difference between each predicted value \hat{y}_i and the actual observed value y_i . The summation of these absolute differences across all data points provides a cumulative measure of error, which is then normalized by the number of observations, n . [8,24,96–98].

The result is a non-negative value that represents the average magnitude of errors in the same units as the data, making it straightforward to understand and communicate. A lower MAE indicates a model with more accurate predictions. The MAE is widely used in a variety of fields, from finance to weather forecasting, and it is especially favored when the costs of positive and negative errors are roughly equivalent [8,24,96–98]

Additional Qualitative Tests

To further investigate the impact of data granularity on the predictive models and to also assess traditional time series models against deep learning models, I adopted a qualitative approach that involved a visual examination of the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) distributions for models trained on daily versus weekly data and for traditional versus deep learning models. The analysis was conducted by observing the error distribution traits using Kernel Density Estimat(KDE) plots.

RESULTS

ASSESSING THE SEASONALITY/CYCLIC PATTERNS

The results of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller(ADF) tests as shown in Table 4.1 indicate various levels of stationarity across the three countries. For the initial ADF test, none of the data achieved stationarity thus indicating the presence of trends and seasonality in the data. However, after applying second differencing, several data series achieved stationarity confirming the presence of unit roots in the original data.

For confirmed cases, the US and France data showed signs of stationarity after the second differencing implying that the time series could be made stationary by removing trends and seasonal effects. India's confirmed cases did not achieve stationarity even after second differencing. The death cases in the US and India reached stationarity after the second differencing while France required only one differencing. The recovered cases in the US were stationary at the outset but the data for India and France required second differencing to achieve stationarity.

The Autocorrelation Function(ACF) and Partial Autocorrelation Function(PACF) graphs were plotted for the relevant countries to understand the data's seasonality or cyclic patterns. However, due to the non-stationary nature of the confirmed case data for India, its ACF and PACF plots have been excluded from this analysis. Also, in order to avoid redundancy, the analysis of the STL decomposition plot has been excluded from this research.

Table 4.1: A. Stationarity Test Results for Confirmed Cases, Deaths, and Recovered Cases

Category	ADF Statistic	p-value	1%	5%	10%	Stationarity
Confirmed Cases						
2*US	1.0265	0.9945	-3.4594	-2.8743	-2.5736	Not Stationary
	-2.9587	0.0389	-3.4595	-2.8744	-2.5736	Stationary after 2nd diff.
2*India	-2.0519	0.2643	-3.4594	-2.8743	-2.5736	Not Stationary
	-1.7039	0.4291	-3.4594	-2.8743	-2.5736	Not Stationary after 2nd diff.
2*France	-2.2169	0.2002	-3.4589	-2.8741	-2.5735	Not Stationary
	-3.1218	0.0250	-3.4589	-2.8741	-2.5735	Stationary after 2nd diff.
Deaths						
2*US	-0.2277	0.9351	-3.4594	-2.8743	-2.5736	Not Stationary
	-3.4532	0.0093	-3.4594	-2.8743	-2.5736	Stationary after 2nd diff.
2*India	-1.3246	0.6179	-3.4582	-2.8738	-2.5733	Not Stationary
	-10.7146	3.2665×10^{-19}	-3.4582	-2.8738	-2.5733	Stationary after 2nd diff.
2*France	-1.3341	0.6134	-3.4592	-2.8742	-2.5735	Not Stationary
	-2.8913	0.0464	-3.4592	-2.8742	-2.5735	Stationary after 2nd diff.
Recovered Cases						
2*US	-15.5541	2.0819×10^{-28}	-3.4576	-2.8735	-2.5731	Stationary
	-15.5541	2.0819×10^{-28}	-3.4576	-2.8735	-2.5731	Stationary
2*India	-1.4112	0.5769	-3.4586	-2.8740	-2.5734	Not Stationary
	-3.4836	0.0084	-3.4595	-2.8744	-2.5736	Stationary after 2nd diff.
2*France	-1.0825	0.7220	-3.4594	-2.8743	-2.5736	Not Stationary
	-3.4836	0.0084	-3.4595	-2.8744	-2.5736	Stationary after 2nd diff.

ACF and PACF FOR US Confirmed Cases

Appendix A, Figure A.1 depicts the ACF and PACF plots for confirmed cases in the US. The ACF plot for confirmed COVID-19 cases in the US was negative at lag 1. Positive auto correlations were noted at lags 7 and 14 and 29. A negative auto correlation at lag 9 and a positive one at lag 29 were also observed with the auto correlation at lag 1. The PACF plot depicts a negative auto correlation at lag 1 and positive correlations at lags 8, 14, 15, 22, and 29 .

ACF and PACF For France Confirmed Cases

In Appendix A, Figure A.2 shows the ACF and PACF for France Confirmed Cases. The ACF plot for France had negative correlations at lags 1 and 2. It also had a negative correlation at lag 9 and the positive correlation at lag 10 . The most significant correlation was at lag 1. The PACF plot showed negative correlations from lags 1 through 6 and positive correlations at lags 8, 10, and 12 . The most pronounced peak was at lag 3.

ACF AND PACF for US Death Cases

In Appendix A, Figure A.3 shows the ACF and PACF for US Death Cases. The ACF plot for death cases in the US shows negative auto correlations at lags 2, 3, 4, 5, 9 and 12 and positive auto correlation at lag 7 (the longest lollipop), 14, 21 and 28 . There is negative auto correlation at lag 16 and the positive one at lag 21. The PACF plot shows negative correlations at lags 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6, with the strongest correlation at lag 5. there are positive significant correlations at lags 7, 12 and 22 in the PACF plot also.

ACF and PACF For India Death Cases

In Appendix A, Figure A.4 shows the ACF and PACF for India Death Cases. The ACF plot for India death cases shows a significant negative auto correlation at lag 1. This is the only significant point in the ACF plot. The PACF plot exhibits a different pattern with significant negative correlations at lags 1 through 6 and the most pronounced correlation is at lag 1.

ACF and PACF For France Death Cases

In Appendix A, Figure A.5 shows the ACF and PACF for France Death Cases. The ACF plot for France death cases shows negative auto correlations at lags 1 and 2 followed by positive auto correlations at lags 3 and 4. The most significant positive auto correlation is observed at lag 7. Significant autocorrelations are also observed at lags 14, 21 and 28 with negative correlations appearing at lags 8, 9, 12, 13 and 16, and positive correlations at 21 and 28. The PACF plot shows significant negative correlations at lags 1, 2, 3, and 6 with the strongest negative correlation at lag 6. Positive correlations appear at lags 13, 15 and 17. There are negative correlations from lag 22 through 29.

ACF and PACF For US Recovered Cases

In Appendix A, Figure A.6 shows the ACF and PACF for US Recovered Cases. The ACF plot for US recovered shows significance only at lag -1 with a negative autocorrelation. The PACF plot shows significant negative correlations at lags 1 through 6 and lags 25 through 30.

ACF and PACF For India Recovered Cases

In Appendix A, Figure A.7 shows the ACF and PACF for India Recovered Cases. For the recovered cases of COVID-19 in India, the interpretation of the ACF and PACF plots is distinct and points to different characteristics in the data. The ACF plot exhibits significant positive auto correlations at a wide range of lags from 1 through 22. The PACF plot for India shows only two significant lags at 1 and 2 both positive.

ACF and PACF For France Recovered Cases

In Appendix A, Figure A.8 shows the ACF and PACF for France Recovered Cases. The ACF plot shows negative autocorrelations at lags 1, 2 and 3, positive auto correlations at lag 7 and further positive correlations at lags 14 and 22 and a negative autocorrelation at lag 11. The PACF plot reveals a series of negative correlations at lags 1 through 6 and lag 8, with the strongest at lag 5. A significant negative correlation at lag 13 and a positive correlation at lag 15 and a significant negative correlation at lag 28 was also noticed.

B. DAILY VS WEEKLY MAE ANALYSIS

Before examining the quantitative impact of data it is important to show the results of the optimal parameters selected for each one of the models used. The ARIMA parameters (p , d , q) which define the structure of the model, are presented in In Appendix A ,Table A.1. Appendix A, Table A.3 below shows the parameters used to adjust the prophet model's sensitivity to trends and seasonalities. Appendix A, Table A.4 depicts the number of neurons and the learning_rate for the RNN model. Appendix A, Table A.5 shows the number of neurons and learning_rate for the LSTM model.

Table 4.2: Mean Absolute Error (MAE) for Daily and Weekly Confirmed Cases

Model	MAE for Daily Confirmed Cases			MAE for Weekly Confirmed Cases		
	US	India	France	US	India	France
ARIMA	59 942.50	2300.69	8545.58	112 904.59	2039.36	7270.43
Prophet	60 223.80	1683.48	10 028.44	113 628.20	3122.22	7570.19
RNN	56 690.05	2812.70	7849.13	110 343.37	1743.15	4680.81
LSTM	62 996.92	2584.29	8813.73	114 973.59	3314.13	6931.40

Table 4.2 above clearly depicts the comparison of the performance of the four models used across the three countries when predicting daily and weekly confirmed COVID-19 cases.

For daily confirmed cases in the US, the RNN with 50 neurons and learning rate of 0.01 out performed other models with an MAE of 56,690.05 . In India, the prophet model performed better than other models with an MAE of 1,683.48, a change point prior scale of 0.01 and seasonality prior scale of 0.1. In France, the RNN model with 50 neurons and learning rate of 0.01 out performed other models to achieve the lowest MAE of 7849.13.

For weekly confirmed cases in the US, the RNN with 50 neurons and learning rate of 0.01 outperformed other models with the lowest MAE of 110,343.37. For India, the RNN model with 50 neurons and learning rate of 0.01 effectively performed better than other models with an MAE of 1,743.15. In France, the RNN model with 50 neurons and learning rate of 0.01 out performed other models in predicting confirmed cases with an MAE of 4680.81 .

Daily vs Weekly Death Cases

Table 4.3 depicts the comparison of the performance of the four models used across the three countries when predicting daily and weekly death COVID-19 cases.

Table 4.3: MAE for Daily and Weekly Death Cases

Model	MAE for Daily Death Cases			MAE for Weekly Death Cases		
	US	India	France	US	India	France
ARIMA	553.09	32.82	274.25	1007.83	43.33	44.41
Prophet	582.72	33.84	221.72	986.84	20.70	45.42
RNN	604.53	30.65	332.30	1038.98	20.59	55.87
LSTM	526.04	42.18	259.76	1010.45	22.13	73.06

For daily death cases in the US, the LSTM with 2 layers and 50 units per layers performed better than other models with an MAE of 526.04. For India, the RNN model with 100 neurons and 0.01 outperformed other models with an MAE of 30.65. The Prophet with a change point prior scale of 0.1 and seasonality prior scale of 1.0. performed better than other models for France with an MAE of 221.72

For weekly deaths cases in the US, the prophet with a change point prior scale of 0.1 and seasonality prior scale of 0.01 performed better than other models with an MAE of 986.84 while the RNN with 100 neurons and 0.001 outperformed other models in India with an MAE of 20.59. For France weekly deaths, the ARIMA(0,0,1) performed better than other models with an MAE of 44.41

Daily VS Weekly Recovered Cases

Table 4.4 shows the comparison of the performance of the four models used across the three countries when predicting daily and weekly recovered COVID-19 cases.

In reviewing the results of the daily recovered cases in the US, the ARIMA(0,0,1) model outperformed the other models with an MAE of 743.14 while the prophet model performed better than other models in India(change point prior scale of 0.1 and seasonality prior scale of 0.01) and France (change point prior scale of 0.5 and seasonality prior scale of 1.0) with an MAE of 2643.48 and 174.36 respectively.

For weekly recovered cases, the RNN with 50 neurons and 0.001 learning rate performed better than the other models in the US with an MAE of 9056.01. In India and France, the prophet model outperformed other models with an MAE of 40,258.13 (with change point prior scale of 0.5 and seasonality prior scale of 0.01)and 481.65(change point prior scale of 0.5 and seasonality prior scale of 0.01) respectively.

Table 4.4: MAE for Daily and Weekly Recovered Cases

Model	MAE for Daily Recovered Cases			MAE for Weekly Recovered Cases		
	US	India	France	US	India	France
ARIMA	743.14	2863.31	206.49	1 544 420.32	49 936.77	610.77
Prophet	21 191.74	2643.48	174.36	390 678.30	40 258.13	481.65
RNN	240 517.61	3284.50	324.18	9056.01	50 514.20	755.15
LSTM	40 197.56	4263.02	296.07	373 534.57	165 521.83	491.42

Table 4.5 shows the overview of the model with the lowest MAE per country and category. To further understand the relationship between the predicted and the actual values, see attached file FinalCode.pdf

Table 4.5: Overview of Model with Lowest MAE per Country and Category

Category	United States	India	France
Daily Confirmed Cases	RNN	Prophet	RNN
Weekly Confirmed Cases	RNN	RNN	RNN
Daily Deaths	LSTM	RNN	Prophet
Weekly Deaths	Prophet	RNN	ARIMA
Daily Recovered	ARIMA	Prophet	Prophet
Weekly Recovered	RNN	Prophet	Prophet

Qualitative Comparison OF MAE Distribution: Daily VS Weekly

Figure 4.1, presents a comparison of Mean Absolute Error (MAE) distributions for models based on daily and weekly COVID-19 data. The blue solid straight line, representing daily data, shows a mean MAE of 16,831.29, suggesting a closer alignment

of predictions to actual values while the weekly data, marked by the red dashed line, has a significantly higher mean MAE of 87,750.73 which suggests a lower accuracy in predictions.

Figure 4.1: Comparison of MAE Distribution: Daily Vs Weekly

The skewness metrics, 4.18 for daily and 4.41 for weekly data indicate a right-skewed distribution for both suggesting the presence of outliers or larger errors. The difference in mean MAE values between daily and weekly data models highlights the superior prediction capabilities of daily data models. A lower mean MAE for daily data suggests these models are generally more accurate aligning more closely with actual values. The slightly higher skewness in the weekly data emphasises a marginally greater impact of outliers indicating that these models while generally reliable may be more prone to significant deviations in some instances.

Qualitative Comparison of MAE Distribution; Traditional VS Deep Learning Models

Figure 4.2 shows a comparative analysis of the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) between traditional and deep learning predictive models. The traditional models with a mean MAE of 67,980.97 and a skewness of 5.21, suggest a distribution with many smaller

errors and an extended tail of high error outliers. On the other hand, the deep learning models shown in purple achieve a lower mean MAE of 36,601.06 and exhibit a skewness of 3.11, pointing to a more concentrated distribution of errors around a lower mean and a reduced occurrence of outliers. The comparison clearly indicates that deep learning models on average not only provide better performance but also yield more consistent predictions with fewer extreme deviations from the actual values.

Figure 4.2: Comparison of MAE Distribution: Traditional Vs Deep Learning Models

DISCUSSION

Investigating the Temporal Dynamics

The exploratory data analysis section of this study has obviously shown the changing pattern of the COVID-19 pandemic data. For instance, it revealed significant decreases in the United States' recovery rates in mid- December 2021, in contrast to India's rapidly increasing recovery rate. These observations align with Ranjan et al's research, that suggests that the obvious difference in recovery rates in the US are due to various health factors and how differently states have responded to the pandemic especially regarding stay at home orders [99]. Ranjan et al. also found that India's recovery rates are climbing much faster than in other countries [99].

The temporal dynamics of COVID-19 revealed during the exploratory data analysis show the relationship between the virus' spread and the possible impact of public health measures. These dynamics which are marked by variations in confirmed cases, recovery rates and mortality draw attention to the pandemic's influence across different countries. This complexity further supports findings by Kapitsinis et al [100] who stipulated that the pandemic's effects are not uniform across nations, with discrepancies likely due to "physical connectivity and the diffusion of coronavirus" [100]. In the United States, the fluctuation of confirmed cases initially pointed to possible containment. However later fluctuations appeared to show the challenges faced in curbing the spread of the virus. India's declining growth rate in confirmed cases may indicate very effective containment strategies which is in line with Beyer et al [101] who noted that the Indian

government, in response to the escalating threat of COVID-19 implemented a series of stringent measures aimed at curbing the virus's spread.

For the recovery rates India shows an upward trend suggesting a good recovery process but the United States experienced a significant downturn in December. This may be due to a failing healthcare system as there was no drop in the pandemic's growth rate for the US. France's mortality rate surpassed those of the United States and India thus raising questions regarding the healthcare system's responsiveness and the possible vulnerability of the population segments (demographics) most affected. These findings indicate that the pandemic's impact is not evenly distributed across countries. This aligns with the thoughts posited by Kapitsinis et al [100], who acknowledged the diversity in pandemic outcomes. The implications of this for predictive modelling is that there may be need to integrate country specific parameters into predictive models.

Presence of Seasonality or Cyclic Patterns

This study's application of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and the subsequent analyses using the Autocorrelation Function (ACF) and Partial Autocorrelation Function (PACF) has provided insights into the behavior of COVID-19 data across the three target countries. The initial ADF tests across the board indicated nonstationarity suggesting the presence of trends and seasonality in the COVID-19 data. Upon applying second differencing, we observed that several data series achieved stationarity particularly for confirmed cases in the US and France and for death cases in both these countries and India. This shift to stationarity after second differencing indicates the presence of unit roots. The fact that India's confirmed cases did not achieve stationarity even after second differencing might point to more complex dynamics being involved and the need to consider more detailed investigation.

For the US, the ACF and PACF plots of confirmed cases show significant autocorrelations at various lags which suggests cyclic patterns. Positive autocorrelations at lags 7, 14 and 29 hint at a weekly cycle in the data, possibly reflecting systematic weekly patterns in reporting or virus spread. Negative autocorrelations at certain lags, like lag 9 further imply periodic deviations from these cycles.

In France, the confirmed cases' ACF plot revealed negative correlations at initial lags, turning positive at later lags, suggesting a complex interplay of factors influencing

case numbers. The noticeable peak at lag 3 in the PACF plot could indicate a short term cyclic pattern in the data.

For death cases, the ACF and PACF plots showed different patterns across the countries. In the US the presence of significant autocorrelations at specific lags (like 7, 14, 21 and 28) in death cases suggests a regular pattern that can possibly be linked to administrative reporting cycles. In contrast, India's death cases showed significant negative autocorrelation only at lag 1 indicating less pronounced cyclic behavior.

The recovered cases in the US, India, and France also displayed varied autocorrelation patterns. The US recovered cases showed significant negative correlations at early lags, suggesting a deviation from a typical cyclic pattern. In contrast, India's recovered cases exhibited significant positive autocorrelations across a wide range of lags indicating strong and consistent cyclic patterns in the recovery data.

Model Performance in Country Prediction

This research presented some unexpected findings that diverge from initial expectations based on previous literature. Prior reviews, including insights from Ceylan et al., led to the anticipation that the ARIMA model would exhibit significant strengths in predicting confirmed COVID-19 cases in France [50]. Contrary to these expectations, it was the RNN model that emerged as the most efficient in this context. Similarly, influenced by the works of Gupta et al [51] and Alzahrani [54] I had anticipated a strong performance from the ARIMA model in the case of India. However, in a surprising turn the RNN model demonstrated superior efficacy outperforming ARIMA in the accuracy of its predictions.

An evaluation of the predicted versus actual graphs(see Finalcode.pdf) for confirmed COVID-19 cases in the United States for RNN suggests a potential avenue for enhancing model accuracy. This observation aligns with the methodologies proposed by Barman et al. [55] and Istaiteh et al [56] which advocate for the integration of multiple models to better fit complex data patterns.

Impact of Data Granularity

Lower mean MAE value were observed for the daily data models suggesting a higher degree of precision and alignment with actual values. In contrast, the higher mean MAE

for the weekly data models points to a reduced accuracy. The skewness showed that both daily and weekly data models exhibit a predominance of smaller errors, however the higher skewness in the weekly data models reflects a greater occurrence of large errors. This indicates that while the weekly models can be generally reliable they may occasionally produce predictions that deviate significantly from actual values. Such deviations could be attributed to the aggregated nature of weekly data, which might mask critical daily fluctuations in pandemic trends.

Traditional Vs Deep Learning Models

The comparative analysis of Mean Absolute Error (MAE) distributions between traditional and deep learning models shows that the traditional models which had a higher mean MAE and greater skewness suggest a tendency for many small errors and a likelihood of occasional large errors. This pattern indicates that while traditional models can be reliable, they may occasionally produce significantly inaccurate predictions.

On the other hand, the deep learning models demonstrate a markedly lower mean MAE and reduced skewness suggesting a tighter clustering of errors around a lower mean and a diminished frequency of large deviations. This indicates that deep learning models are not only more accurate on average but also offer more consistent predictions.

Limitations and Future Research Directions

Given the results and discussions above, there are areas for further research directions. For instance, expanding the data to include more countries and a longer timeline could yield deeper insights, especially when looking into the cyclical nature of the virus. Also, including variables such as vaccination rates, population demographics, public health policies, and social mobility could enhance model predictions. Future research directions could also look at creating hybrid models. An additional limitation in my modeling approach was the exclusion of holiday effects in the Prophet model due to data unavailability. This omission may have affected the accuracy of predictions, especially in capturing short term variations influenced by holidays and special events. Future research should focus on including such variables to improve the models accuracy.

CONCLUSION

This research aimed to analyse the temporal dynamics and patterns of COVID-19, focusing on confirmed cases, deaths and recovery rates using advanced time series techniques. By examining the data from the United States, France and India. The research revealed that the COVID-19 pandemic exhibited distinct temporal patterns with significant fluctuations in death, recovery rates and confirmed cases across different countries. Also, the presence of seasonality and cyclic patterns in COVID-19 data was identified. The application of time series analysis tools such as the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test and Autocorrelation Functions indicated non stationarity in the data suggesting underlying trends and seasonal influences. This was particularly evident in the United States and France where confirmed and death cases showed cyclic patterns, possibly reflecting systematic reporting or virus spread trends.

The study also assessed the influence of data granularity on predictive models. The difference between daily and weekly data was found to significantly impact model accuracy. In comparing traditional time series models with deep learning models, this research found that Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) outperformed models like ARIMA in forecasting accuracy.

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APPENDICES

ACF and PACF for Confirmed_US (2nd Differenced)

Figure A.1: ACF and PACF for United States Confirmed Cases

ACF and PACF for Confirmed_France (2nd Differenced)

Figure A.2: ACF and PACF for France Confirmed Cases

Figure A.6: ACF and PACF for US Recovered Cases

Figure A.7: ACF and PACF for India Recovered Cases

Figure A.8: ACF and PACF For France Recovered Cases

Table A.1: Optimal ARIMA Orders for Daily and Weekly COVID-19 Data

Metric	Country	Optimal ARIMA Order(p,d,q)
Daily Confirmed	US	(2, 0, 2)
Daily Confirmed	India	(3, 1, 2)
Daily Confirmed	France	(3, 0, 3)
Daily Deaths	US	(4, 0, 5)
Daily Deaths	India	(0, 0, 1)
Daily Deaths	France	(2, 0, 1)
Daily Recovered	US	(0, 0, 0)
Daily Recovered	India	(0, 2, 2)
Daily Recovered	France	(2, 0, 2)
Weekly Confirmed	US	(1, 0, 0)
Weekly Confirmed	India	(1, 0, 0)
Weekly Confirmed	France	(1, 0, 0)
Weekly Deaths	US	(0, 1, 2)
Weekly Deaths	India	(1, 0, 0)
Weekly Deaths	France	(0, 0, 1)
Weekly Recovered	US	(0, 0, 1)
Weekly Recovered	India	(1, 1, 0)
Weekly Recovered	France	(0, 0, 1)

Table A.2: Optimal ARIMA Orders for Daily and Weekly COVID-19 Data

Table A.3: Best Parameters for Prophet Model

Metric	Country	Changepoint Prior Scale	Seasonality Prior Scale
Daily Confirmed	US	0.1	1.0
Daily Confirmed	India	0.01	0.1
Daily Confirmed	France	0.5	0.1
Daily Deaths	US	0.1	1.0
Daily Deaths	India	0.5	0.01
Daily Deaths	France	0.1	1.0
Daily Recovered	US	0.01	0.01
Daily Recovered	India	0.1	0.01
Daily Recovered	France	0.5	1.0
Weekly Confirmed	US	0.1	0.01
Weekly Confirmed	India	0.5	0.01
Weekly Confirmed	France	0.1	0.01
Weekly Deaths	US	0.1	0.01
Weekly Deaths	India	0.5	0.01
Weekly Deaths	France	0.5	0.01
Weekly Recovered	US	0.1	0.01
Weekly Recovered	India	0.5	0.01
Weekly Recovered	France	0.5	0.01

Table A.4: Best Parameters for RNN Models

Metric	Country	Neurons	Learning Rate
Daily Confirmed	US	50	0.01
Daily Confirmed	India	50	0.01
Daily Confirmed	France	50	0.01
Daily Deaths	US	100	0.001
Daily Deaths	India	100	0.01
Daily Deaths	France	100	0.001
Daily Recovered	US	50	0.01
Daily Recovered	India	100	0.001
Daily Recovered	France	100	0.01
Weekly Confirmed	US	50	0.001
Weekly Confirmed	India	50	0.01
Weekly Confirmed	France	50	0.01
Weekly Deaths	US	50	0.001
Weekly Deaths	India	100	0.001
Weekly Deaths	France	100	0.01
Weekly Recovered	US	50	0.001
Weekly Recovered	India	100	0.001
Weekly Recovered	France	100	0.01

Table A.5: Best Parameters for LSTM Models

Metric and Country	LSTM Layers	Units per Layer
Daily Confirmed US	2	50
Daily Confirmed India	2	50
Daily Confirmed France	2	50
Daily Deaths US	2	50
Daily Deaths India	2	50
Daily Deaths France	2	50
Daily Recovered US	2	50
Daily Recovered India	2	50
Daily Recovered France	2	50
Weekly Confirmed US	2	50
Weekly Confirmed India	2	50
Weekly Confirmed France	2	50
Weekly Deaths US	2	50
Weekly Deaths India	2	50
Weekly Deaths France	2	50
Weekly Recovered US	2	50
Weekly Recovered India	2	50
Weekly Recovered France	2	50
